

Stability Analysis of the CMFD-Based PCQS Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present a Predictor-Corrector Quasi-Static (PCQS) method, in which the conventional point-kinetics model is replaced by a Coarse Mesh Finite Difference (CMFD) diffusion solver serving as the corrector. Numerical analyses are provided to examine the stability of the CMFD-based PCQS algorithm, offering insights into its performance and potential advantages for reactor kinetics simulations.

Keywords: Fourier analysis, CMFD, PCQS, transport eigenvalues

1. INTRODUCTION

The QS algorithm is a computational reactor physics method, that improves efficiency by separating the neutron flux into a fast-changing amplitude function and a slow-changing shape function. It “predicts” the flux shape using a “high-order” space-time neutron transport solver over relatively large (“macro”) time steps, then “corrects” the amplitude using a “low-order” calculation over smaller (“micro”) time steps to account for changes in the flux. This approach significantly speeds up simulations of reactor kinetics compared to fully space-time dependent transport methods [1,2].

The PCQS method, as shown in Figure 1a, is a factorization scheme that, unlike the traditional QS method, does not require iterative solutions of the shape and amplitude functions. Instead, the neutron flux is first computed directly in the predictor step, followed by a correction using the amplitude function evaluated in the corrector step [3].

A novel PCQS approach based on the Transient MultiLevel (TML) methodology has recently been proposed and successfully demonstrated for transient reactor analysis [4,5,6]. The core concept of the TML method is to resolve flux changes across space, energy, and angle within distinct time domains that reflect their physical variation during transients. At the intermediate level, the PCQS method facilitates coupling between the CMFD diffusion solver and the Exact Point Kinetics Equation (EPKE) solver, enabling fine-resolution flux variation capture. This multilevel strategy permits the use of coarser time steps for the transport solver, which typically dominates computational cost.

Although the TML algorithm has proven effective in solving reactor kinetics problems, a theoretical analysis of its numerical properties remains absent. To address this gap, this paper presents a detailed numerical investigation of a simplified variant, the CMFD-PCQS method, in which the third EPKE level is removed—without loss of generality, as illustrated in Figure 1b. We examine its stability to offer valuable insights into its performance and potential benefits for reactor kinetics simulations. If a higher-order time integration scheme is used for the CMFD calculation, our analysis indicates that the third EPKE level can be omitted, making the scheme even more computationally efficient and attractive—particularly for Monte Carlo applications, where the adjoint flux calculation is no longer required.

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Figure 1. PCQS algorithm.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the CMFD-PCQS algorithm based on the monoenergetic transport equation with isotropic scattering in slab geometry. The backward Euler method is used for time discretization, and spatial discretization employs the classic Diamond Difference (DD) method. Section 3 presents numerical analyses, including Fourier analysis for the stability of the algorithm. In Section 4, a numerical example involving a positive reactivity insertion is provided to demonstrate the effectiveness of the CMFD-PCQS algorithm. A concluding summary is provided in Section 5.

2. CMFD-PCQS ALGORITHM

Our model problem is a homogeneous monoenergetic neutron transport problem with isotropic scattering and periodic boundary conditions in one-dimensional (1D) slab geometry. Both the transport and CMFD solve the so-called transient fixed-source problem (TFSP), which consists of the coupled time-discretized neutron and precursor balance equations. The transport neutron flux is calculated over “macro” time steps and is corrected by the CMFD flux, which is solved over “micro” time steps.

The methodology for the coupled transport and CMFD calculation is described below. Standard notation is employed, and definitions are omitted for brevity unless clarification is necessary.

- 1) Perform the transport prediction calculation over the l -th time step:

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi^l(x, \mu, t)}{\partial t} + \mu \frac{\partial \psi^l(x, \mu, t)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_t \psi^l(x, \mu, t) = \frac{1}{2} \Sigma_s \phi^l(x, t) + \frac{1}{2K_0} (1 - \beta) v \Sigma_f \phi^l(x, t) + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k C_k^l(x, t), \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_k^l(x, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{K_0} \beta_k v \Sigma_f \phi^l(x, t) - \lambda_k C_k^l(x, t), \quad (1b)$$

where

$$\phi(x, t) = \int_{-1}^1 \psi(x, \mu, t) d\mu, \quad (1c)$$

$$\beta = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k . \quad (1d)$$

- 2) Perform the CMFD correction calculation over the m -th time step within the l -th transport step:

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \Phi^{l,m}(x,t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial J^{l,m}(x,t)}{\partial x} + \Sigma_a \Phi^{l,m}(x,t) = \frac{1}{K_0} (1 - \beta) v \Sigma_f \Phi^{l,m}(x,t) + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k \mathbb{C}_k^{l,m}(x,t), \quad (2a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbb{C}_k^{l,m}(x,t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{K_0} \beta_k v \Sigma_f \Phi^{l,m}(x,t) - \lambda_k \mathbb{C}_k^{l,m}(x,t), \quad (2b)$$

where $m = 1, \dots, M = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta t_{CMFD}}$. Δt is the macro transport time step size, and Δt_{CMFD} is the micro CMFD time step size.

$$J^{l,m} = \widehat{D}^{l,m} \Phi^{l,m} - D \frac{\partial \Phi^{l,m}}{\partial x}, \quad (2c)$$

$$\widehat{D}^{l,m} = \widehat{D}^{l-1} + \frac{\widehat{D}^l - \widehat{D}^{l-1}}{M} \left(m - \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad (2d)$$

with

$$\widehat{D}^{l-1} = \frac{J^{l-1} + D \frac{d\phi^{l-1}}{dx}}{\phi^{l-1}}, \quad \widehat{D}^l = \frac{J^l + D \frac{d\phi^l}{dx}}{\phi^l} \quad (2e)$$

It is noted that the nonlinear current correction coefficient $\widehat{D}^{l,m}$ used in the CMFD calculation is obtained through linear interpolation between the current valued computed from the predicted transport flux and that from the previous time step. Alternative interpolation methods may also be employed.

In addition, the initial conditions for the CMFD calculation: $\Phi^{l,0} = \phi_c^{l-1}$ and $\mathbb{C}_k^{l,0} = \mathbb{C}_{k,c}^{l-1}$, where ϕ_c^{l-1} and $\mathbb{C}_{k,c}^{l-1}$ are, respectively, the corrected flux and precursor concentration from the previous transport time step.

- 3) Perform the flux and delayed neutron precursor correction:

$$\psi_c^l = \psi^l \frac{\Phi^{l,M}}{\phi^l}, \quad (3a)$$

$$C_{k,c}^l = \mathbb{C}_k^{l,M}, \quad (3b)$$

where the corrected transport angular flux ψ_c^l is obtained by multiplying the predicted angular flux ψ^l by the ratio of the CMFD scalar flux to the predicted transport scalar flux, $\Phi^{l,M}/\phi^l$. The CMFD flux $\Phi^{l,M}$ is obtained after performing M time integrations. Note that in this analysis, the CMFD solution employs the same mesh as the transport calculation, although a coarser mesh could also be used for CMFD.

3. STABILITY ANALYSIS

The von Neumann analysis (Fourier analysis) is employed to perform stability analysis of the CMFD-PCQS algorithm. To facilitate Fourier analysis, the 1D homogeneous model problem is formulated with periodic boundary conditions (BCs). We first need to linearize the CMFD equation, as it is inherently nonlinear, whereas the neutron transport equation is linear. We then perform a Fourier analysis of the linearized, coupled transport and CMFD equations to derive the amplification matrix, which typically depends on the time step size and mesh size.

3.1. Linearization of CMFD

The unknowns of the model problem are defined by introducing small perturbations around the unperturbed solution:

$$\psi(x, \mu, t) = \psi_0(x, \mu) + \varepsilon\psi_1(x, \mu, t), \quad (4a)$$

$$\phi(x, t) = \phi_0(x) + \varepsilon\phi_1(x, t), \quad (4b)$$

$$J(x, t) = \int_{-1}^1 \mu\psi(x, \mu, t)d\mu = \int_{-1}^1 \mu(\psi_0(x, \mu) + \varepsilon\psi_1(x, \mu, t))d\mu = J_0(x, t) + \varepsilon J_1(x, t), \quad (4c)$$

$$\Phi(x, t) = \Phi_0(x) + \varepsilon\Phi_1(x, t), \quad (4d)$$

$$C_k(x, t) = C_{k0}(x) + \varepsilon C_{k,1}(x, t), \quad (4e)$$

$$\mathbb{C}_k(x, t) = \mathbb{C}_{k0}(x) + \varepsilon\mathbb{C}_{k,1}(x, t). \quad (4f)$$

By substituting Eqs. (4b) and (4c) into Eq. (2e), respectively, we first linearize \widehat{D}^{l-1} and \widehat{D}^l .

$$\widehat{D}^{l-1} \approx \frac{J_0^{l-1} + D \frac{d}{dx} \phi_0^{l-1}}{\phi_0^{l-1}} + \varepsilon \frac{J_1^{l-1} + D \frac{d}{dx} \phi_1^{l-1}}{\phi_0^{l-1}}, \quad (5a)$$

$$\widehat{D}^l \approx \frac{J_0^l + D \frac{d}{dx} \phi_0^l}{\phi_0^l} + \varepsilon \frac{J_1^l + D \frac{d}{dx} \phi_1^l}{\phi_0^l}. \quad (5b)$$

We now demonstrate that \widehat{D} is predominantly determined by the spatial shape of the neutron flux and thus remains nearly constant over the duration of a macro transport time step. To see this, we separate the angular flux $\psi(x, \mu, t)$ into the shape function $\Psi(x, \mu, t)$ and the amplitude function $T(t)$:

$$\psi(x, \mu, t) = T(t)\Psi(x, \mu, t). \quad (6)$$

Substituting Eq. (6) into the \widehat{D} formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{D} &= \frac{J + D \frac{d\phi}{dx}}{\phi} = \frac{\int_{-1}^1 \mu\psi d\mu + D \frac{d}{dx} \int_{-1}^1 \psi d\mu}{\int_{-1}^1 \psi d\mu} = \frac{T \int_{-1}^1 \mu\Psi d\mu + TD \frac{d}{dx} \int_{-1}^1 \Psi d\mu}{T \int_{-1}^1 \Psi d\mu} \\ &= \frac{\int_{-1}^1 \mu\Psi d\mu + D \frac{d}{dx} \int_{-1}^1 \Psi d\mu}{\int_{-1}^1 \Psi d\mu}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The fast-changing amplitude function has been canceled out in the calculation. Numerical tests further confirm that the variation of \widehat{D} within a macro time step is somewhat negligible. Therefore, we can simply let $\widehat{D}^{l,m} \approx \widehat{D}^{l-1}$ (or \widehat{D}^l) in stability analysis.

Substituting Eqs. (4d), (4e), and (5a) into Eq. (2a), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial(\Phi_0^{l,m} + \varepsilon\Phi_1^{l,m})}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{J_0^{l-1} + D \frac{d}{dx} \phi_0^{l-1}}{\phi_0^{l-1}} + \varepsilon \frac{J_1^{l-1} + D \frac{d}{dx} \phi_1^{l-1}}{\phi_0^{l-1}} - D \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right] (\Phi_0^{l,m} + \varepsilon\Phi_1^{l,m}) \\ + \Sigma_a(\Phi_0^{l,m} + \varepsilon\Phi_1^{l,m}) = \frac{1}{K_0} (1 - \beta)v\Sigma_f(\Phi_0^{l,m} + \varepsilon\Phi_1^{l,m}) + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k (\mathbb{C}_{k0}^{l,m} + \varepsilon\mathbb{C}_{k,1}^{l,m}). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

For the periodic BCs, $\Sigma_a = \frac{1}{K_0} v\Sigma_f$. After some algebra and dropping the subscript "1", Eq. (8) is

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial\Phi^{l,m}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(J^{l-1} + D \frac{d}{dx} \phi^{l-1} - D \frac{\partial\Phi^{l,m}}{\partial x} \right) = -\frac{1}{K_0} \beta v\Sigma_f \Phi^{l,m} + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k \mathbb{C}_k^{l,m}. \quad (9)$$

3.2. Discretization

To perform Fourier analysis, the transport equation, Eq. (1a) is typically discretized using the DD or Step Characteristic (SC) method on a uniform mesh of size h , as shown in Figure 2. The precursor balance equation is a simple ordinary differential equation, which is solved together with the transport solution. The backward Euler method is used for time integration.

Figure 2. 1D mesh.

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\psi_j^l - \psi_j^{l-1}}{\Delta t} + \mu \frac{\psi_{j+1/2}^l - \psi_{j-1/2}^l}{h} + \Sigma_t \psi_j^l = \frac{1}{2} \Sigma_s \phi_j^l + \frac{1}{2K_0} (1 - \beta) \nu \Sigma_f \phi_j^l + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k C_{k,j}^l, \quad (10a)$$

$$\frac{C_{k,j}^l - C_{k,j}^{l-1}}{\Delta t} = \frac{1}{K_0} \beta_k \nu \Sigma_f \phi_j^l - \lambda_k C_{k,j}^l. \quad (10b)$$

The linearized CMFD equation, along with its precursor equations, is discretized on the same mesh as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v} \frac{\Phi_j^{l,m} - \Phi_j^{l,m-1}}{\Delta t_{CMFD}} + \frac{J_{j+1/2}^{l-1} - J_{j-1/2}^{l-1}}{h} + D \frac{\phi_{j-1}^{l-1} - 2\phi_j^{l-1} + \phi_{j+1}^{l-1}}{h^2} - D \frac{\Phi_{j-1}^{l,m} - 2\Phi_j^{l,m} + \Phi_{j+1}^{l,m}}{h^2} \\ = -\frac{1}{K_0} \beta \nu \Sigma_f \Phi_j^{l,m} + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k C_{k,j}^{l,m}, \end{aligned} \quad (11a)$$

$$\frac{C_k^{l,m} - C_k^{l,m-1}}{\Delta t_{CMFD}} = \frac{1}{K_0} \beta_k \nu \Sigma_f \Phi_j^{l,m} - \lambda_k C_k^{l,m}. \quad (11b)$$

3.3. Fourier Analysis

We introduce the following Fourier ansatz:

$$\phi_j^l = \zeta^l e^{i\Sigma_t \omega x_j}, \quad (12a)$$

$$\psi_j^l = \zeta^l a(\mu) e^{i\Sigma_t \omega x_j}, \quad \text{where } \int_{-1}^1 a(\mu) d\mu = 1, \quad (12b)$$

$$\psi_{j\pm 1/2}^l = \zeta^l b(\mu) e^{i\Sigma_t \omega x_{j\pm 1/2}}, \quad (12c)$$

$$C_{k,j}^l = \gamma_k^l \frac{\beta_k \nu \Sigma_f}{K_0 \lambda_k} e^{i\Sigma_t \omega x_j}, \quad (12d)$$

$$\Phi_j^{l,m} = \eta^m \phi_j^{l-1} = \eta^m \zeta^{l-1} e^{i\Sigma_t \omega x_j}, \quad (12e)$$

$$C_k^{l,m} = \Gamma_k^m \frac{\beta_k \nu \Sigma_f}{K_0 \lambda_k} \zeta^{l-1} e^{i\Sigma_t \omega x_j} = \Gamma_k^m \frac{\beta_k \nu \Sigma_f}{K_0 \lambda_k} \phi_j^{l-1}. \quad (12f)$$

Note that the factor of $\frac{\beta_k \nu \Sigma_f}{K_0 \lambda_k}$ in Eq. (12d) and (12f) is used to simplify the Fourier transformed precursor equations.

We first perform Fourier analysis of the neutron transport equation. By substituting Eqs. (12a-d) into Eq. (10a), after some algebra we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v} \frac{\zeta^l a(\mu) - \zeta^{l-1} a(\mu)}{\Delta t} + \mu \frac{\zeta^l b(\mu) e^{\frac{i\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}} - \zeta^l b(\mu) e^{-\frac{i\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}}}{h} + \Sigma_t \zeta^l a(\mu) \\ = \frac{1}{2} \Sigma_s \zeta^l + \frac{1}{2K_0} (1 - \beta) \nu \Sigma_f \zeta^l + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k \gamma_k^l \frac{\beta_k \nu \Sigma_f}{K_0 \lambda_k}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Integrating the above equation with respect to μ , we obtain

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\zeta^l - \zeta^{l-1}}{\Delta t} + \frac{2}{h} i \sin\left(\frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}\right) \zeta^l \int_{-1}^1 \mu b(\mu) d\mu + \Sigma_a \zeta^l = \frac{1}{K_0} (1 - \beta) v \Sigma_f \zeta^l + \sum_{K=1}^K \gamma_k^l \frac{\beta_k v \Sigma_f}{K_0}. \quad (14)$$

Note that we have used $\int_{-1}^1 a(\mu) d\mu = 1$ in Eq. (12b), and $e^{\frac{i\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}} - e^{-\frac{i\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}} = 2i \sin\left(\frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}\right)$.

Recalling $\Sigma_a = \frac{1}{K_0} v \Sigma_f$, after rearrangement we can further simplify the above equation as

$$\left(1 + \frac{v\Delta t}{K_0} \beta v \Sigma_f - 2 \frac{v\Delta t}{h} i \sin\left(\frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}\right) \int_{-1}^1 \mu b(\mu) d\mu\right) \zeta^l - v\Delta t \frac{v\Sigma_f}{K_0} \sum_{K=1}^K \gamma_k^l \beta_k = \zeta^{l-1}. \quad (15)$$

By substituting Eqs. (12a) and (12d) into Eq. (10b), after some algebra we obtain

$$(1 + \lambda_k \Delta t) \gamma_k^l - \lambda_k \Delta t \zeta^l = \gamma_k^{l-1}. \quad (16)$$

We can rewrite Eqs. (15) and (16) in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{P}^l = \mathbf{A}^{-1} \mathbf{P}^{l-1}, \quad (17)$$

where

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_1 \\ \vdots \\ \gamma_K \\ \zeta \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \lambda_1 \Delta t & \cdots & & -\lambda_1 \Delta t \\ & \ddots & & \\ & & 1 + \lambda_K \Delta t & -\lambda_K \Delta t \\ -v\Delta t \frac{\beta_1 v \Sigma_f}{K_0} & \cdots & -v\Delta t \frac{\beta_K v \Sigma_f}{K_0} & C \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18a)$$

with

$$C = 1 + \frac{v\Delta t}{K_0} \beta v \Sigma_f - 2 \frac{v\Delta t}{h} i \sin\left(\frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}\right) \int_{-1}^1 \mu b(\mu) d\mu, \quad (18b)$$

where C is a complex number. From Eqs. (12b) and (12c), we can find $b(\mu) = a(\mu) \sec \frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2}$ for the DD discretization.

We rewrite Eq. (17) as

$$\mathbf{P}^l = \mathbf{G} \mathbf{P}^{l-1} = \mathbf{G}^l \mathbf{P}^0, \quad (19)$$

where the amplification matrix $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{G}(\Delta t, h, \omega) = \mathbf{A}^{-1}$. The stability requirement is that \mathbf{G}^l should be uniformly bounded for all ω with real components [7]. Let the eigenvalues of \mathbf{G} be $\alpha^{(i)}$, $i = 1, \dots, K + 1$. The von Neumann stability condition requires the spectral radius of \mathbf{G} : $r = r(\Delta t, h, \omega) = \text{Max}_{(i)} |\alpha^{(i)}|$ to satisfy

$$\text{Max}_{(\omega)} |r(\Delta t, h, \omega)| \leq 1 + O(\Delta t). \quad (20)$$

If the spectral radius of the matrix \mathbf{A} is larger than or equal to one, then the above stability condition can be met in a more restrictive sense. We now use the Gershgorin theorem to obtain a sufficient condition for the matrix \mathbf{A} to ensure all its eigenvalues larger than or equal to one, i.e., if $a_{i,i} \geq 1 + \sum_{j \neq i} |a_{i,j}|$, where $a_{i,i}$ is the i -th diagonal entry of the matrix \mathbf{A} .

For the first K diagonal entries of the matrix \mathbf{A} ,

$$1 + \lambda_i \Delta t \geq 1 + |-\lambda_i \Delta t| = 1 + \lambda_i \Delta t, \quad i = 1, \dots, K, \quad (21)$$

and for the last diagonal entry, the real part of the complex number C

$$1 + \frac{v\Delta t}{K_0} \beta v \Sigma_f \geq 1 + \sum_{j \neq K+1} |a_{K+1,j}| = 1 + \frac{v\Delta t}{K_0} \beta v \Sigma_f. \quad (22)$$

Therefore, there is no restriction on the time-step size, confirming that the first-order implicit Euler method is unconditionally stable.

Next, we perform Fourier analysis of the CMFD calculation. By substituting Eqs. (12a), (12e), and (12f) into Eqs. (11a) and (11b), after some algebra we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(1 + 4D \frac{v\Delta t_{CMFD}}{\Delta x^2} \sin^2 \frac{\Sigma_t \omega \Delta x}{2} + \frac{v\Delta t_{CMFD}}{K_0} \beta v \Sigma_f\right) \eta^m - v\Delta t_{CMFD} \frac{v\Sigma_f}{K_0} \sum_{k=1}^K \Gamma_k^m \beta_k \\ &= \eta^{m-1} + 4D \frac{v\Delta t_{CMFD}}{\Delta x^2} \sin^2 \frac{\Sigma_t \omega \Delta x}{2} - 2 \frac{v\Delta t_{CMFD}}{h} i \sin \frac{\Sigma_t \omega \Delta x}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \mu b(\mu) d\mu, \end{aligned} \quad (23a)$$

$$(1 + \lambda_k \Delta t_{CMFD}) \Gamma_k^m - \lambda_k \Delta t_{CMFD} \eta^m = \Gamma_k^{m-1}. \quad (23b)$$

We can rewrite Eqs. (23a) and (23b) in matrix form as

$$\mathbf{X}^m = \mathbf{B}^{-1} \mathbf{X}^{m-1} + \mathbf{B}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ E \end{bmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

where

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_1 \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma_K \\ \eta \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 + \lambda_1 \Delta t_{CMFD} & \cdots & & -\lambda_1 \Delta t_{CMFD} \\ & \ddots & & \\ & & 1 + \lambda_K \Delta t_{CMFD} & -\lambda_K \Delta t_{CMFD} \\ -v\Delta t_{CMFD} \frac{\beta_1 v \Sigma_f}{K_0} & \cdots & -v\Delta t_{CMFD} \frac{\beta_K v \Sigma_f}{K_0} & F \end{bmatrix} \quad (25a)$$

and

$$E = 4D \frac{v\Delta t_{CMFD}}{h^2} \sin^2 \frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2} - 2 \frac{v\Delta t_{CMFD}}{h} i \sin \frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \mu b(\mu) d\mu, \quad (25b)$$

$$F = 1 + 4D \frac{v\Delta t_{CMFD}}{h^2} \sin^2 \frac{\Sigma_t \omega h}{2} + v\Delta t_{CMFD} \frac{\beta v \Sigma_f}{K_0}. \quad (25c)$$

As for the transport matrix \mathbf{A} above, we can use the Gershgorin theorem to obtain a sufficient condition for the matrix \mathbf{B} to have all its eigenvalues larger than or equal to one. It is easy to confirm that the CMFD scheme with first-order backward Euler integration is unconditionally stable; however, an adequate time step should be used to maintain accuracy.

4. A NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

In this section, we present a numerical example to illustrate the effectiveness of the CMFD-PCQS method. The test case is a homogeneous, monoenergetic neutron transport problem with isotropic scattering and vacuum boundary conditions in a 1D slab geometry. The slab has a thickness of 100 cm. The transport solution is computed using DD spatial discretization, Gauss–Legendre S_{12} angular quadrature, and first-order backward Euler time integration. A positive reactivity insertion was simulated by uniformly reducing the absorption cross section in the slab reactor. The solutions were computed using various time step sizes, with the reference solution employing a very fine time step of 0.01 s. For each transport time step, the CMFD solutions calculated over 10 and 20 substeps, respectively, were applied to correct the S_n transport solution.

This example demonstrates that the CMFD correction enables the use of larger time steps in transport calculations, thereby significantly accelerating transient simulations, as shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, the CMFD correction reduces the predicted transport error to the order of $O(\Delta t/M)$, where M denotes the number of substeps within each transport time step. If a higher-order time integration scheme is applied to the CMFD calculation, fewer substeps will be required.

Figure 3. The power increase due to a positive reactivity insertion.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we conducted a numerical analysis of the CMFD-based PCQS method, which has been proposed for reactor kinetics calculations. The effectiveness of the QS method relies on factorizing the flux into an amplitude function and a shape function, with the amplitude varying much more rapidly than the shape. A von Neumann stability analysis was employed to derive the amplification matrix, from which the stability criterion in terms of the spectral radius for the algorithm can be computed. A sufficient stability condition was derived using the Gershgorin theorem, showing that there is no restriction on the time-step size and therefore confirming that the CMFD-PCQS scheme with first-order backward Euler integration is unconditionally stable. Finally, a numerical example is provided to demonstrate the algorithm's efficiency.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Henry. "The Application of Reactor Kinetics to the Analysis of Experiments." *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **3**, pp. 52–70 (1958).
- [2] K. O. Ott and D. A. Menley. "Accuracy of the Quasi-static Treatment of Spatial Reactor Kinetics." *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **36**, pp. 402–411 (1969).
- [3] S. Dulla, E. H. Mund, and P. Ravetto. "The Quasi-Static Method Revisited." *Prog. Nucl. Energy*, **50**, pp. 908–920 (2008).
- [4] A. Zhu, Y. Xu, and T. Downar. "A Multilevel Quasi-Static Kinetics Method for Pin-Resolved Transport Transient Reactor Analysis." *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **182**, pp. 435–451 (2016).
- [5] F. Abdullatif and D. Wang. "A Multilevel Quasi-Static Kinetics Module for Monte Carlo Simulations." *Trans. Am. Nucl. Soc.*, **128**, pp. 252–255 (2023).
- [6] F. Abdullatif and D. Wang. "Implementation and Assessment of the Crank-Nicolson Method for the Monte Carlo Multilevel Kinetics Module." In *Proceedings of the PHYSOR-2024*. American Nuclear Society, San Francisco, CA, USA (2024).
- [7] P. D. Lax and R. D. Richtmyer. "Survey of the Stability of Linear Finite Difference Equations." *Comm. Pure Appl. Math.*, **IX**, pp. 267–293 (1956).